

RADx-UP Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2)

January 1, 2022 – June 30, 2022

Interim Evaluation Report

September 8, 2022

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Abbreviations

CCPH	Campus Community Partners for Health
CDCC	Coordination and Data Collection Center
CHER	UNC Center for Health Equity Research
C2G	Community Collaboration Grant
DA	Data Analytics
DEI	Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion
EO	Evaluation Objective
EQ	Evaluation Question
MSC	Most Significant Change
NIH	National Institutes of Health
PI	Principal Investigator
RADx-UP	Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics - Underserved Populations
RP2	Rapid Research Pilot Program
SEBI	Social, ethical, and behavioral implications
SECDP	Stakeholder Engagement, Communication, and Dissemination Plan
SEP	Strategic Evaluation Plan
T&E	Tracking & Evaluation
UNC	The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
US	United States

Executive Summary

The Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics - Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) Program aims to ensure that all Americans, particularly those from underserved and vulnerable communities most affected by COVID-19, have access to COVID-19 testing to reduce the disparities in COVID-19-associated morbidity and mortality. The Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2) aims to award up to \$200,000 used within a 12-month period to continuously and responsively assess the feasibility of utilizing implementation strategies, community-based interventions, and multi-level partnerships to increase the reach, access, acceptance, uptake, and sustainment of FDA-authorized/approved COVID-19 diagnostics among vulnerable populations in geographic locations that are underserved in coordination with the NIH-supported RADx initiatives¹. Institutions of higher education, industry, state and local governments, and community-based organizations with the infrastructure to manage such funding are eligible to apply for the RP2 funding¹. RP2s are human subject research studies requiring approval from an Institutional Review Board (IRB).

This interim evaluation report details the RADx-UP Rapid Research Pilot Program's (RP2) key evaluation findings that indicate RADx-UP RP2 program outputs, outcomes, productivity, and impacts between January 2022 through June 30, 2022. This report also presents an opportunity for collaboration with RADx-UP, Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC), and NIH stakeholders to establish evaluation feedback loops for identifying and addressing areas of improvement.

The tracking and evaluation (T&E) team at the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill (UNC) employs a longitudinal design utilizing a mixed-methods approach. The T&E team collects data on project updates, activities, outcomes, and CDCC support and resources used by the awardees at seven time points (see [Appendix 1 for the RADx-UP RP2 Evaluation Logic Model](#)). The T&E team is responsible for distributing the bimonthly surveys, analyzing the data, and communicating the results to RP2 leadership and other stakeholders.

RP2 Program Evaluation Overview

The outputs, outcomes, productivity, and impact of the RP2 program were measured using data already collected by the CDCC (project intake & characteristics), publicly available publication data, and evaluation surveys.

- As of June 30, 2022, the CDCC has funded 13 RP2 projects across four funding cycles.
 - The projects are separated by cycle, with cycle one projects beginning in August/September of 2021, cycle two projects beginning in November 2021, and cycle four projects beginning in March 2022.
- This report is reporting on data from cycle one, cycle two, and cycle four projects. There were no funded projects for cycle three.
- While the successful application rate has increased, the number of applicants per cycle appears to be decreasing, and cycle three did not have any applicants. The Testing Core has discussed mitigation to increase the low number of RP2 applications.
- Most RP2 projects are in the Midwest, South, and Southwest regions (see figure 1).
- The most common underserved populations targeted by the RP2 projects include socioeconomically disadvantaged people, people living in nursing homes and assisted living facilities, and Hispanic/Latino populations.

RP2 Project Geographic Diversity (figure developed by the American Institutes for Research (AIR) for RADx-UP)

Program Enrollment

- As of June 30, 2022 the RP2 projects have enrolled 870 participants of the 8,130 that they're targeting to enroll.
 - The RP2 Project Total Number of Participants Enrolled: Actual and Target breaks down participant enrollment numbers by cycle.

RP2 Project Total Number of Participants Enrolled: Actual and Target

Program Testing

- **RP2 projects have administered a total of 2,207 tests.** Of this total, there have been 56 positive tests in cycle one or 2.6% of tests in cycle one and 2.5% across cycles. Cycle two and cycle four have not yet reported any positive tests as of June 30, 2022.
- The *RP2 Project Total Number of Tests Administered: Actual and Target* figure breaks down the total number of tests performed and the total number of tests planned to administer by cycle.

Challenges and Barriers

- The most common challenges reported by the projects (n=12) include **administrative issues** such as delays in receipt of funding, hiring and contract establishing, **and pandemic-related delays** such as COVID-related lockdowns in study settings which delay data collection.

Recommendations

Based on these findings, the T&E team provides two main recommendations for improving the RP2 program. These recommendations aim to support continuous program improvement, program delivery, and quality of administrative support.

1. **Continue to fund a diverse range of projects to maximize the impact, effectiveness, and efficiency of RADx-UP CDCC to ensure that all Americans, particularly those from underserved and vulnerable communities most affected by COVID-19, have access to COVID-19 testing to reduce the disparities in COVID-19-associated morbidity and mortality.**
 - Focus marketing and communication efforts on recruiting additional applicants for future cycles
 - Continue to fund projects representing geographically diverse, underserved, and Covid-19 vulnerable communities. Some populations to focus on recruiting in the future can include –
 - West, Northwest, and Eastern regions of the US
 - Recruiting projects that represent tribal nations

2. Address challenges cited by projects

- Projects report challenges related to participant enrollment, administrative tasks such as funding and staffing, testing reporting, and testing administration.
- Of the 12 projects that reported on challenges experienced, **the most common were related to administrative challenges and pandemic-related delays.**
 - *Administrative challenges* include releasing funding from NIH, hiring and training staff, and non-testing resource procurement.
 - *Pandemic-related challenges* are defined as challenges that arise because of changing social distancing requirements and employees contracting COVID-19.
- Maintaining **continuous feedback loops** between the UNC T&E team, the RP2 implementation team, and RP2 awardees

Feedback loops between T&E team, RP2 leadership team, and RP2 awardees

I. Background

The Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics - Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) Program aims to ensure that all Americans, particularly those from underserved and vulnerable communities most affected by COVID-19, have access to COVID-19 testing to reduce the disparities in COVID-19-associated morbidity and mortality.

The program seeks to achieve this primary aim through:

- Understanding and alleviating barriers to testing across the nation
- Utilizing implementation strategies, community-based interventions, and multi-level partnerships to increase the reach, access, acceptance, uptake, and sustainment of FDA-authorized/approved diagnostics among vulnerable populations in geographic locations that are underserved
- Strengthening the available data on disparities in infection rates, disease progression, and outcomes; differences in testing access and uptake patterns; and identifying strategies to address inequities in COVID-19 diagnostics

The RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC) supports RADx-UP projects as they serve their communities and serve as the technical support system and infrastructure to maximize the impact and effectiveness of all projects within the RADx-UP program. The Duke Clinical Research Institute (DCRI) and the Center for Health Equity Research (CHER) at the University of North Carolina (UNC), Chapel Hill, oversee the CDCC.

This 2022 Interim RP2 Evaluation Report explicitly covers the evaluation of **the RADx-UP Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2)** projects from January 1 through June 30, 2022. In coordination with the National Institutes of Health (NIH) supported RADx initiatives¹, the **Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2)** awards up to \$200,000 in or direct costs for a 12-month period to continuously and responsively assess the feasibility of utilizing implementation strategies, community-based interventions, and multi-level partnerships to increase the reach, access, acceptance, uptake, and sustainment of FDA-authorized/approved COVID-19 diagnostics among vulnerable populations in geographic locations that are underserved¹. Institutions of higher education, industry, state and local governments, and community-based organizations with the infrastructure to manage such funding are eligible to apply for the RP2 funding¹. RP2s are human subject research studies requiring approval from an Institutional Review Board (IRB).

These evaluation results are used by the RP2 team to address any issues with awardees in ad hoc meetings and to improve CDCC support and overall understanding of each project's progress towards reaching their intended goals.

Overview of the RADx-UP RP2 Evaluation

The Tracking and Evaluation (T&E) team at the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill (UNC), comprehensively assesses the RADx-UP program's productivity and impact by evaluating its

projects. The T&E team employs the core components of the **Translational Science Benefits (TSBM) Model**² to assess the translation of innovation related to COVID-19 testing into clinical applications, healthcare guidelines, community interventions, policies, and other outcomes that benefit underserved communities at large. The team also employs the **Most Significant Change (MSC) approach** to better understand program impact, and the values held by different stakeholders³. An overview of the RADx-UP RP2 aims, outcomes and associated evaluation key measures are available in [Table 1](#).

The T&E team also monitors and evaluates how the CDCC program activities improve the RADx-UP program’s effectiveness, performance, and community engagement.

The purpose of this report is two-fold: 1) describe key evaluation findings that indicate **RADx-UP RP2 program** outputs, outcomes, productivity, and impacts; and 2) collaborate with RADx-UP, CDCC, and NIH stakeholders to establish evaluation feedback loops for identifying and addressing areas of improvement.

Table 1. Overview of RADx-UP RP2 Aims, Outcomes, and Associated Evaluation Key Measures

Overview of Outcomes and Key Measures		
Outcomes	Measures	Survey Tools Used
Aim 1: Improve access to and uptake of diagnostic COVID-19 testing in underserved, COVID-19 medically, geographically, and socially vulnerable populations		
Increase in individuals reached with testing services or information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of individuals reached through projects (enrolled) • Number of individuals tested • Number of positive tests • Frequency of testing per participant • Number of participants showing one or more symptoms • Underserved populations and COVID-19 vulnerable populations engaged through projects (per cycle and cumulatively) • Diversity of populations reached (geographically, across underserved and vulnerable population categories) 	Bimonthly evaluation surveys via REDCap
Aim 2: Evaluate the feasibility of implementing emerging COVID-19 testing technologies in underserved communities		

<p>Participants enrolled in each study</p> <p>Expanded RADx-UP Resource Library</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diversity of organizations funded (location, organization type) # of new materials/resources added to Resource Library Number and type of research products resulting from pilot project (publication, new external grant, etc.) 	<p>Program Records</p> <p>Bimonthly evaluation surveys via REDCap</p>
<p>Aim 3: Implement the RP2 program to maximize the impact, effectiveness, and efficiency of RADx-UP CDCC to ensure that all Americans, particularly those from underserved and vulnerable communities most affected by COVID-19, have access to COVID-19 testing to reduce the disparities in COVID-19-associated morbidity and mortality.</p>		
<p>Recruitment of a sufficient number of applicants</p> <p>Timely launch of projects</p> <p>Timely completion of projects</p> <p>Feedback on utility and quality support</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # of applicants per cycle # of projects awarded per cycle # of days between award notification and project initiation Utilization of RADx-UP resources and support % of awardees that expended funding in a 12-month grant period Types of CDCC support used Suggested improvements to CDCC support/resources 	<p>Program Records</p> <p>Bimonthly evaluation surveys via REDCap</p>

II. Methods

Data Sources. The evaluation of RADx-UP RP2 consists of a longitudinal evaluation design, which involves collecting data from RP2 program awardees at seven time points. Data collection included gathering data on project updates, activities, outcomes, and use of CDCC support and resources (see [Appendix 1 for the RADx-UP RP2 Evaluation Logic Model](#)). Data sources include RP2 program records, project intake surveys, bimonthly evaluation surveys, and an 18-month follow-up survey. See [figure 1](#) for a flow diagram of how the data sources map onto program evaluation.

RP2 Program Records

The RP2 grant administration leadership team works with the T&E team to provide grant administration data such as the number of applicants per cycle.

Project Intake Survey

The T&E team retrieves demographic data on the project target population(s) and project characteristics from the Project Intake Survey completed by the project team.

Bimonthly Evaluation Surveys

The T&E team administers bi-monthly progress report surveys through REDCap to RP2 awardees based on project start dates (2-month initial survey, 4-month, 6-month interim, 8-month, 10-month, and 12-month closeout). Evaluation Surveys collect information on project testing and enrollment, challenges faced in completing the program; protocol changes; and tracking self-assessment on meeting milestones.

The 6-month and 12-month surveys contain additional questions to gather data on project outcomes, research productivity and dissemination of findings; utilization of RADx-UP CDCC support; and community partner engagement. Items on these evaluation surveys also assess outcomes and impacts with respect to the TSBM Framework indicators.

Follow-up Survey (18 months)

The T&E team administers a follow-up survey at 18 months (six months after project completion) via REDCap to assess the long-term impacts of the pilot projects. This evaluation includes any sustained project activities and other achievements from the pilot project (such as additional external funding, new partnerships, new publications, etc.). Items on this evaluation survey also assess outcomes and impacts with respect to the MSC approach.

Figure 1. Evaluation Data Sources

Data Analysis. The T&E team analyzes data and shares the findings with the RP2 leadership via dashboard and evaluation reports.

Individual Dashboards

The T&E team summarizes the data findings from the bimonthly surveys (per awardee) into individualized data summaries/dashboards and shares them with the RP2 team before the subsequent data collection time point.

Quarterly Aggregate Dashboards

The T&E team aggregates survey data across projects (included data are from projects' most recent completed survey) into quarterly dashboards that contain information about:

- Communities served
- Partner organization types
- Project enrollment and testing numbers
- Challenges reported
- Research products developed
- CDCC Impact and satisfaction

See [Appendix 2](#) for the most recently developed RADx-UP RP2 Quarterly Dashboard Report.

Biannual T&E Evaluation Reports

The T&E team analyzes data from all bi-monthly surveys across projects and presents the findings in biannual evaluation reports. The T&E team codes open-ended response items as categorical variables. Qualitative data include questions about project challenges, roadblocks, and improvements to RADx-UP CDCC support or resources.

Project Impact Profiles. The T&E team utilizes 6 and 12-month survey data to create Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM) Project impact profiles⁴. The RP2 and the T&E teams will co-develop each project's profile with the respective project. The profiles provide a high-level description of how project outcomes reported on the 12-month survey align with impact areas of the model, as shown in the [figure 2](#) below.

The TSBM is a framework designed to support the assessment of clinical and translational research outcomes to measure clinical and community health impacts² (see [Figure 2](#)). The T&E Team will use the core components of the TSBM to evaluate the impact of the RP2 program in demonstrating the clinical, community, economic, and policy benefits of investing in increased access to COVID-19 testing, vaccination, and community-led engagement initiatives in underserved communities. The main contribution of the TSBM is its utility in identifying the core areas where testing outreach and strategies developed through the RADx-UP program provide clinical, public health, economic, and policy benefits. The T&E team will also include an

additional impact indicator – health equity, to describe the impact profiles of projects that focus on dismantling inequities in testing among underserved populations.

Figure 2. Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM) + Health Equity Impact Areas³

 CLINICAL	Clinical and Medical Benefits (procedures, guidelines, tools, and products)
 COMMUNITY	Community and Public Health Benefits (health activities, care, and promotion)
 ECONOMIC	Economic Benefits (commercial products, financial savings, and benefits)
 HEALTH EQUITY	Health Equity Benefits* (accessibility, adaptability, reach)
 POLICY	Policy and Legislative Benefits (advisory activities, policies, and legislation)

*The TSBM Framework has been adapted for this evaluation to include an indicator for Health Equity benefits.

Most Significant Change. The Most Significant Change (MSC) technique is an evaluation method that involves collecting significant change stories from the field, and having a panel of designated stakeholders select the most significant of these stories³. This informs program impact and unintended changes, how and when a change came to be, and also helps provide an understanding on the values of different stakeholders. The MSC approach will be incorporated into the 18-month follow up survey. The survey will include an open text question asking respondents to share what they felt was the most significant change that resulted from their project.

III. Results

This evaluation reports details the results from the bi-monthly RP2 (2-month, 4-month, and 6-month) surveys collected between January 1 through June 30, 2022, and analyzed and summarized across projects.

A. Process Evaluation Results

RP2 Program Grant Application Process and Award Utilization

Currently, there are **13 RP2 projects across funding cycles** (Cycle 1 n=8 funded projects; Cycle 2 n=1 funded project; there were no funded projects in Cycle 3, Cycle 4 n=4 funded projects).

[Table 2](#) below shows the metrics per RP2 funding cycle for the application process and notification of awards. While the successful application rate has increased, the number of applicants per cycle appears to be decreasing, and cycle three did not have any applicants. The Testing Core has discussed mitigation to increase the low number of RP2 applications.

The average number of days between award notification and project initiation varied by cycle. For cycles 1 and 2, we used the Notice of Award (NoA) date for award notification. For cycle 4 and all cycles moving forward, we will use the activation date rather than the NoA date, as NIH no longer requires the NoA date for projects deemed less than minimal risk by their IRB of record. Removing the NoA requirement reduced the average number of days between award notification and project initiation.

Table 2. Metrics per RP2 Funding Cycle for the Grant Application Process, Notification of Award, and Funding Expenditure by Awardees

RP2 Project Cycle	Application Period	Number of Applicants per cycle	Number of Projects Awarded per cycle	Successful Application Rate	Average number of days between award notification and Project initiation
Cycle 1	3/3/21 – 5/28/21	9	8	88.8%	182
Cycle 2	5/7/21 - 8/2/21	5	1	20%	79
Cycle 3	6/19/21 - 8/13/21	0	0	-	-
Cycle 4	10/29/21 - 2/1/22	8	4	50%	60 [^]
Cycle 5*	4/1/22 – 7/8/22	3	3	100%	-

*Cycle 5 projects have not yet begun and are not included in this report.

[^]The number reflects the average of three of the four awarded projects in the cycle. The fourth project was excluded because the average number of days between award notification and project initiation (160 days) was significantly longer than the other three projects.

In this report, we present data from 2-month, 4-month, and 6-month timepoints for:

- Cycle 1 n=8 of 8 total projects
- Cycle 2 n =1 of 1 total project
- Cycle 4 n= 3 of 4 total projects

Satisfaction with CDCC Administration Resources and Support. Figure 3 summarizes the results from the 6-month survey regarding project satisfaction with the application and award process. Overall, projects reported satisfaction with RADx-UP CDCC administration's support regarding the application process. **At least 75 percent of respondents agreed or strongly agreed with each statement** that asked about receiving adequate support to completing their application and having an RFA that was easy to understand and accessible to projects. Appendix 3 provides additional figures to display the data from project satisfaction with application and award process results.

Figure 3. RP2 Project Satisfaction with CDCC Administration Resources and Support (n= 8 projects reporting)

B. Outcome Evaluation Results

B1. Sociodemographic Results

Characteristics of RP2 Projects

Geographic Diversity. RP2-funded Projects are spread out throughout the US, with the majority located in the Midwest, South, and Southwest regions. Figure 4 below shows the geographic diversity of RP2 Projects across the United States (US).

Figure 4. RP2 Project Geographic Diversity: Total Number of Rapid Pilot Projects by State as of April 25, 2022 (n= 13) (figure developed by the American Institutes for Research (AIR) for RADx-UP)

Institution Type. Figure 5

reflects the RP2 project institution type. The T&E team retrieved this information from the Integrated Postsecondary Education Data System and other US Department of Education resources⁵⁻⁷. Of the projects that reported this data, cycle one projects

included Asian American and Native American Pacific Islander-serving institutions and Hispanic-serving institutions. Of the cycle four projects that reported this information, the only institution type reported was Historically Black College and University institution.

Figure 5. RP2 Project Institution Type (n= 12* projects reporting)
 *A total of 12 projects reported on institution type, but only five total fell within the categories included in the figure
 Cycle 1: n = 3 projects, Cycle 4: n= 2 projects

Underserved Populations Served. See [Figure 6](#) for a breakdown of underserved populations served by RP2 projects. Underserved populations are *populations that the NIH has identified as being underrepresented in biomedical research and known to experience greater morbidity and mortality because of socioeconomic factors*⁸. **This data shows that RP2 projects have a broad**

reach of underserved populations- all populations that fall within underserved populations are being reached. Of the projects reported during this reporting period, **the most common underserved population served by RP2 projects were socioeconomically disadvantaged populations.**

Figure 6. Underserved Populations Served by Projects (*n= 12 projects reporting*)
Cycle 1: n = 8 projects, Cycle 2: n = 1 project, Cycle 4: n = 3 projects

Figure 7. COVID-19 Vulnerable Communities Served by Projects (*n= 12 projects reporting*)
Cycle 1: n = 8 projects, Cycle 2: n = 1 project, Cycle 4: n = 3 projects

COVID-19 Vulnerable Communities Served. See [Figure 7](#) for a breakdown of COVID-19 vulnerable communities served by RP2 projects. COVID-19 vulnerable communities are *populations that the NIH has identified as being at greater risk of COVID-19 infection and poor health outcomes*

*from COVID-19*⁹. When taken together, **RP2 projects have a wide reach of COVID-19 vulnerable communities;** all communities that fall within the COVID-19 vulnerable communities are being reached. Of the projects reported during this period, **residents of nursing homes and assisted living facilities were the most common COVID-19 vulnerable communities served by RP2 projects.**

Figure 8. Characteristics of RP2 Projects' Partners (n= 7 projects reporting)
 Cycle 1: n = 6 projects, Cycle 2: n = 1 project

Characteristics of RP2 Projects' Partners. Figure 8 refers to the project's community partner organizations. Data is collected during the 6-month interim survey. Seven total projects have responded to this question, most from cycle one. **Most project partners are classified as community organizations or faith-based organizations.**

B2. RP2 Project Testing and Enrollment Outcomes

RP2 Projects Testing and Enrollment. One of the main aims of the RP2 program is to improve access to and uptake of diagnostic COVID-19 testing in underserved, medically, geographically, and socially vulnerable populations. Figure 9 shows the target participant enrollment number as well as the number of participants enrolled across cycles one, two, and four. This data informs the program outcome of increasing numbers of individuals reached with testing services or information. Of the nine projects reported, **there have been a total of 870 participants enrolled.** When taken together, the cumulative total for target enrollment for cycle one projects is 4,560 participants. Cycle two's target enrollment is 120 participants, and has already achieved this goal.

Figure 10 shows the number of tests administered versus planned to administer versus actually administered to participants across eleven projects, with **a total of 1,923 tests administered.** Of this total, there have been 56 positive tests in cycle one, or 2.6% of tests in cycle one and 2.5% across cycles. Cycle two and cycle four have not yet reported any positive tests.

Figure 9. Number of Participants Enrolled: Actual vs Target (n= 9 projects reporting)
 Cycle 1: n = 5 projects, Cycle 2: n = 1 project, Cycle 4 : n= 3 projects

Figure 10. Number of Tests Administered: Actual vs Target (n= 11 projects reporting)
 Cycle 1: n = 7 projects, Cycle 2: n = 1 project, Cycle 4 : n= 3 projects

Challenges Experienced by Projects. The T&E team also asked projects to report on any roadblocks or challenges faced so far in completing their project. The survey includes noting challenges relating to sample collection, challenges to testing, test result reporting, and engaging with community members. The T&E team reviewed these challenges and coded the responses into several categories.

Of the 12 projects that reported on challenges experienced, **the most common were related to administrative challenges and pandemic-related delays.** *Administrative challenges* include releasing funding from NIH, hiring and training staff, and non-testing resource procurement. *Pandemic-related challenges* are defined as challenges that arise because of changing social distancing requirements and employees contracting COVID-19. [Table 3](#) lists the codes that the T&E team developed for responses to questions that ask projects *to describe any challenges to sample collection, testing, test result reporting, engaging with community members, and any other challenges not mentioned.*

As challenges are observed, the T&E team is communicating these challenges to leadership so they can be addressed promptly. Testing reporting, partnerships, and enrollment challenges may be opportunities for the RP2 team to strategize how to address those challenges with projects.

Table 3. Challenges Experienced by Projects

Code	Quotes
Administrative	<i>"Slow to receive funding"</i> <i>"Delay in contract establishing"</i> <i>"Delay in hiring"</i>
Pandemic-Related Delays	<i>"COVID-related lockdowns in study setting delayed data collection"</i>
Enrollment	<i>"Costs of subject compensation needed to be taken into account"</i> <i>"Community people are not willing to take the tests"</i> <i>"One of our goals was to enroll people who previously experienced homelessness and currently housed in permanent supportive housing, however it has been difficult to reach this group since they are not physically located in the shelter and because we are restricted per IRB to passive recruitment. Therefore, our PSH resident numbers are lower than expected."</i>
Testing Administration	<i>"Difficulties in finding proper locations for testing operation"</i> <i>"Few subjects are willing to provide both saliva samples and nasal swab. most people are not interested in testing in general, or think that vaccine protective, so no need for testing even if they are symptomatic"</i> <i>"Moved testing date to accommodate Ramadan"</i>

Regulatory	"To update the testing method, I submitted a modification form to the UCSF IRB in early February, but there is a delay to get it approved." "IRB approval is our biggest hurdle."
Partnerships	"Engaging community partners is problematic due to budget constraints." "Asylum seekers are a challenging population to reach and asylum serving organizations are often very resource poor. There were some delays in our activities while we established new community partnerships in order to best reach this population."
Testing Procurement	"Costs of Hologic PCR tests needed to be taken into account. More Hologic PCR tests would be helpful to have if they were able to be provided free of cost." "No response from iHealth regarding its rapid antigen test kits."
Testing Reporting	"Some participants don't have email. We have to report the results via phone call or text messages." "At-home testing accuracy"

B3. RP2 Project Outcomes and Impacts

RP2 Project Outcomes Aligned with the Translational Sciences Benefit Model (TSBM)

Indicators. In this section, we summarize the results from the 6-month survey regarding the RP2 project's impacts and plans for sustainability of their research and project activities.

Currently, no projects have yet received their 12-month survey. Still, once these data are collected, the T&E Team will develop Impact Profiles for each project to reflect how project outcomes reported on the 12-month survey align with impact areas of the TSBM framework.

Projects' Research

Products. The T&E team tracks peer-reviewed publications along with other RADx-UP publications in our T&E Publications Tracking. In addition to scholarly publications, the T&E team seeks to

Figure 11. RP2 Research Products (n= 5 projects reporting)
Cycle 1: n = 4 projects, Cycle 2: n = 1 project

understand additional products that projects are developing and disseminating. **Figure 11** breaks down the types of research products that projects have developed.

IV. Recommendations and Conclusion

Recommendations. This section details process and outcome-related recommendations for improving the RP2 program based on conclusions from the bi-monthly surveys. These recommendations aim to support continuous program improvement, delivery, and quality of administrative support.

1. **Continue to fund a diverse range of projects to maximize the impact, effectiveness, and efficiency of RADx-UP CDCC to ensure that all Americans, particularly those from underserved and vulnerable communities most affected by COVID-19, have access to COVID-19 testing to reduce the disparities in COVID-19-associated morbidity and mortality.**
 - Focus efforts on recruiting additional applicants for future cycles- The number of applicants per cycle appears to be decreasing, and cycle three did not have any applicants.
 - Continue to fund projects representing geographically diverse, underserved, and Covid-19 vulnerable communities. Some populations to focus on recruiting in the future include:
 - West, Northwest, and Eastern regions of the US
 - Recruiting projects that represent tribal nations
2. **Address challenges cited by projects**
 - Projects report challenges related to participant enrollment, administrative tasks such as funding and staffing, testing reporting, and testing administration.
 - Of the 12 projects that reported on challenges experienced, the most common were related to administrative challenges and pandemic-related delays.
 - *Administrative challenges* include releasing funding from NIH, hiring and training staff, and non-testing resource procurement.
 - *Pandemic-related challenges* are defined as challenges that arise because of changing social distancing requirements and employees contracting COVID-19.
 - Maintaining continuous feedback loops between the UNC Evaluation team, the implementation team, and RP2 awardees

Conclusion. The T&E team aims to measure and assess the RP2 program's productivity and progress toward program aims and outcomes. The T&E team also monitors and evaluates how the CDCC program activities improve the RP2 program's effectiveness, performance, and community engagement. The T&E team achieves it through bimonthly surveys distributed to funded projects and tracking of program records. The purpose of this interim evaluation report is to cover the evaluation of the RADx-UP Rapid Research Pilot Program (RP2) projects from January 1 through June 30, 2022. Currently, there are 13 RP2 Projects across funding cycles

(Cycle 1 n=8 funded Projects; Cycle 2=1 funded project; there were no funded Projects in Cycle 3, Cycle 4=4 funded Projects). A total of 870 participants have been enrolled, and 2,207 tests have been administered across projects.

Next Steps. In the remainder of the RP2 program, the T&E team will continue to:

1. Monitor program progress through bi-monthly surveys and reports will be completed every six months.
2. Create: (i) Impact Profiles to be shared with each project to highlight project outcomes and benefits and (ii) an Aggregate RP2 Impact Profile to visualize program-level outcomes and TSBM benefits across projects.
3. Additionally, the T&E will distribute an 18-month (six months post-project) survey to assess the longer-term impacts of the pilot projects, including any sustained project activities and other achievements that stemmed from the pilot project (additional external funding, new partnerships, etc.).

References

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Appendix

Appendix 1. RADx-UP RP2 Evaluation Logic Model

Rapid Research Pilots Evaluation Logic Model

Appendix 2. RADx-UP RP2 Quarterly Dashboard Report

Data collected from Jan. 1, 2022 to Jul. 15, 2022. See Appendix for list of projects and timepoints included in the report.

12
Projects Reporting

16
Projects Awarded

Projects by Cycle

Latest Survey Completed by Projects

Projects from Minority-Serving Institutions

Communities Served

40
Underserved Communities

42
COVID-19-Vulnerable Communities

Underserved Communities

COVID-19-Vulnerable Communities

Partner Organization Types

30
Partner Organizations

Partner Organizations by Type

Cumulative Enrollment

870

Participants Enrolled to Date

7,210

Participants to Enrollment Target

Cumulative Testing

5

Testing Projects

Tests Kits Used by Projects

2,143

Tests Administered

53 (2.5%)

Positive Tests

Challenges

35

Challenges Reported

Type of Challenges Reported by Projects

Research Products

11

Research Products

Type of Research Products Reported by Projects

CDCC Overall

Overall Satisfaction with CDCC

CDCC Services

Satisfaction with CDCC Support Services

CDCC Impact

The CDCC support services increased my project's understanding of community engagement approaches

The CDCC support services increased my project's application of community-engagement approaches in connecting with my project's communities

The knowledge gained from the CCPH office hours was useful for my project

Appendix

Tests Kits Used by Projects

Project	Test Kit	Test Type
R0103	Hologic-Panther PCR	PCR
R0103	LDT LAMP	PCR
R0103	Quidel-antigen test	Rapid Antigen
R0104	Abbott BinaxNOW COVID-19 Ag Card	Rapid Antigen
R0105	Abbott BinaxNOW*	Rapid Antigen
R0105	FlowFlex COVID-19 Antigen Home Test	Rapid Antigen
R0107	Quidel QuickVue At-Home antigen tests	Rapid Antigen
R0109	TaqPath 2.0	PCR

Projects Reporting

Project	Cycle	Last Timepoint Completed
R0101A	1	6
R0102A	1	6
R0103A	1	4
R0104A	1	6
R0105A	1	6
R0106A	1	6
R0107A	1	2
R0109A	1	6
R0204A	2	6
R0401A	4	2
R0405A	4	2
R0406A	4	2

Glossary

Minority-Serving Institution: Institutions focused on serving minority students. More information about institution types can be found [here](#).

Abbreviation	Minority-Serving Institution
AANAPI-Serving	Asian American and Native American Pacific Islander-Serving Institution
HBCU	Historically Black College and University
Hispanic-Serving	Hispanic-Serving Institution
Non-MSI	Non-Minority-Serving Institution
TCU	Tribal College or University

Underserved Community: Populations that the NIH has identified as being underrepresented in biomedical research and known to experience greater morbidity and mortality because of socioeconomic factors. More information can be found [here](#) and [here](#).

Abbreviation	Underserved Community
AIAN	American Indians/Alaska Natives
Asian	Asian Americans
Black	Blacks/African Americans
Latino	Hispanics/Latinos
LowSES	Socioeconomically disadvantaged populations
NHPI	Native Hawaiians and other Pacific Islanders
Rural	Rural and remote communities; underserved rural populations
SGM	Sexual and gender minorities

COVID-19 Vulnerable Community: Populations that the NIH has identified as being at greater risk of COVID-19 infection and poor health outcomes from COVID-19. More information can be found [here](#).

Abbreviation	COVID-19 Vulnerable Community
Child	Children and adolescents
Cognition	Individuals with cognitive impairment or dementia, or communication disorders
Comorbidities	Individuals with medical comorbidities known to increase risk of severe COVID-19
Congregate Housing	Individuals living in congregate housing such as shelters or residential treatment facilities
Elderly	Community-dwelling older adults
EnvRisk	Communities exposed to high rates of air pollution or other toxic exposures
Homeless	Homeless populations
Immigrants	Migrant and immigrant communities
MentalHealth	Individuals with substance use disorders or serious mental illness
Pregnant	Pregnant and post-partum women
Public Housing	Individuals in overcrowded or public housing
Rural	Rural and remote communities; underserved rural populations
TribalNation	Residents of tribal lands or reservations

Appendix 3. RP2 Project Satisfaction with CDCC Administration Resources and Support

Figure 3. Satisfaction with the Application and Award Process (n= 8 projects reporting)

